

CASE STUDY

FAIRplus use case IMI EUbOPEN: Open by design saves time

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Challenge

IMI project EUbOPEN, aiming to build a protein binding library, generates large volumes and many different types of data, all of which need to be interlinked and integrated to decide which compounds are to be released as chemical probes to the community.

Background

EUbOPEN is an international consortium of 22 partners from academia and industry, funded by **IMI/IHI**. The goal of EUbOPEN is to create a library of compounds binding to 1,000 proteins. These ~5,000 compounds will be well characterized for their ability to interact with human proteins within their native environment, the cell.

'This library together with the associated publicly available data will allow scientists to probe the function of a specific protein, and aligns with the overarching goal to **be able to study the influence of each human protein by 2035**', says Stefan Knapp, coordinator of EUbOPEN. 'Being able to modulate each protein by a validated compound set, will allow us to unravel the signaling roles in complex cellular systems and to identify new potential targets for medical research and drug development', adds project leader Florian Montel from Boehringer Ingelheim.

EUbOPEN is fully committed to Open Science and thus aims to publish all its generated data open and fully accessible to everyone. Therefore, the EUbOPEN project has been working with experts from the **FAIRplus project** from the start. The IMI FAIRplus project aims to develop tools and guidelines for making life science data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). In the past year, the so-called 'squad teams' from FAIRplus, consisting of experts working in universities and pharmaceutical companies, have been actively working to FAIRify data sets from large IMI projects such as EUbOPEN, APPROACH, eTOX, and COMBINE. The developed tools and methods are subsequently added as 'recipes' to the FAIR Cookbook, enabling projects and companies with similar FAIR data challenges to apply this consolidated know-how to increase the FAIRness of their data.

Goals

The IMI projects to be supported by FAIRplus are selected in an **unbiased process**, based on a recorded set of criteria, among others societal impact. The most important aim of FAIRifying project data is to facilitate sharing data outside the consortium to conduct further research.

EUbOPEN was selected as one of those projects to be FAIRified by the FAIRplus squad teams. 'By adhering to the overarching principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", we make all of our data available as soon as we can', states Susanne Müller-Knapp, COO of the **Structural Genomics Consortium (SGC)**. 'This eliminates some typical

challenges regarding data sharing from the very start. We have many different types of data, all of which need to be interlinked and integrated to really come to conclusions about the compounds we want to release as chemical probes to the community. The FAIR principles help us to organize our data in such a way that this integration, or interoperability, becomes as easy as possible to the end user.'

Amelie Tjaden, scientist at BMLS in Frankfurt, explains the challenges her teams is facing. 'In our lab, we generate data from high-content live-cell multiplex screens. During this process, and over time, we take several images of these cells, and see what effect a compound has on the cells' appearance. This data is especially challenging because it generates high volumes, in the range of terabytes, but also because its evaluation needs to integrate so much other compound data, such as their specific profiling and comparisons to controls.'

Results

Because of EUBOPEN's commitment to Open Science, even before practical work began the project already had a detailed data management plan. This allowed the FAIRplus squad teams to quickly and efficiently gain an overview of the data available, and the data to be generated over the course of the project.

Initially, FAIRification goals needed to be defined and a mechanism how to onboard the project was established. The project then took off and proved to be a 'huge success', in the words of Müller-Knapp. FAIRplus experts Dorothy Reilly and Philip Gribbon add that the initial stages and onboarding are in fact part of the success story, since work with EUBOPEN was valuable for the FAIRplus team to improve their abilities to onboard other projects more efficiently.

'Working together with many individual subject matter experts within the EUBOPEN project, we quickly learned how interdisciplinary their research data is, and how interconnected each dot in the project is', says FAIRplus expert Robert Giessmann from Bayer AG. 'For example, compound identifier management proved to be absolutely crucial to evaluate the results from the multiplex screen. Also, we had to investigate the technical infrastructure very closely to be able to transfer the data out of the local data centers to deposit it in BiImage Archive. Finally, bioactivity information is now to be submitted to ChEMBL, which required deep interactions with the corresponding team there.'

In addition, the FAIRplus squad teams introduced pragmatic Research Data Management solutions in the form of Excel templates, and provided Standard Operating Procedures for actual transfer of the data.

The benefit

The collaboration with FAIRplus was crucial in depositing the data to European online resources and repositories, such as the BiImage Archive, ChEMBL and Zenodo. EUBOPEN can now share their multiplex screen data with everyone, adhering to FAIR principles of openness and interoperability.

Giessmann concludes: 'What makes me really excited about the outcome of our work, is that we were able to create tangible value by simultaneously providing computational tools in the form of Python scripts to automate the evaluation of the complex multiplex screens. This saves EUBOPEN researchers weeks of time they can now spend on creating even more exciting data.'

The FAIRplus squad teams [have summarised their work](#) on this in the [FAIR Cookbook](#). The recipe gives background on the current data standards for high-content multiplex screening, and proposes a pragmatic way to organize the data with minimal effort on the researcher's side.